

Supplementary Material

Table 1: Existing distance measures for FFS in the literature.

Measure	Formula
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{DW}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Deng and Wang (2022)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} + \frac{(v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} \right]}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{DW}2}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Deng and Wang (2022)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left \sqrt{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3} - \sqrt{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} \right ^2 + \left \sqrt{v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3} - \sqrt{v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} \right ^2 \right]}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{AF}1}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Ashraf et al. (2023)	$\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \right]$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{AF}2}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Ashraf et al. (2023)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{AF}3}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Ashraf et al. (2023)	$\frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\max\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \}}{1 + \max\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \}}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{K}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Kirişçi (2022)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2 + (v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2 + (\pi_A^3 - \pi_B^3)^2 \right]}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{S}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Seikh and Mukherjee (2024)	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} + \frac{(v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3} + \frac{(\pi_A^3 - \pi_B^3)^2}{\pi_A^3 + \pi_B^3} \right]}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{Wang}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Wang et al. (2024)	$1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3}{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^6 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^6 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^6 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^6 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{Gao}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Gao et al. (2023)	$1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\min\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\} + \min\{1 - v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, 1 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\}}{\max\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\} + \max\{1 - v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, 1 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\}}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{AL}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Alrasheedi et al. (2024)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3}{2} - \frac{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3}{2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3}{2} - \frac{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3}{2} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{Mi}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Mishra et al. (2024)	$\frac{1}{4n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + \left \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 \right + \left \min\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\} - \min\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3, v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3\} \right + \left \max\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3, v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3\} - \max\{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3, v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3\} \right \right\}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{Liu}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Liu (2024)	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + 2} + \frac{(v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + 2} \right]}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{G}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Ganie et al. (2024)	$\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + \pi_A^3 - \pi_B^3 \right)$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{DE}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Deveci et al. (2024)	$\left(\frac{1}{2n(t+1)^p} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left (t+1-a)(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3) - a(v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3) \right ^p + \left (t+1-b)(v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3) - b(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3) \right ^p \right] \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$
<i>where p is L_p-norm, t, a, and b denote levels of uncertainty with constraint a + b ≤ t + 1, 0 ≤ a, b ≤ t + 1, and t > 0.</i>	
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{PK}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Pathak et al. (2025)	$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2 + (v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3)^2}{\sqrt{1 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3}}$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{PM}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Premalatha and Somasundaram (2025)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 + \pi_A^3 - \pi_B^3 }{4} + \frac{\max\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , \pi_A^3 - \pi_B^3 \}}{2} \right]$
$\mathcal{D}_{\text{Li}}(\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ Li et al. (2025)	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2 \min\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \}}{1 + \min\{ \mu_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - \mu_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 , v_{\mathcal{F}_1}^3 - v_{\mathcal{F}_2}^3 \}} \right)$

Table 2: Existing score functions on Fermatean fuzzy sets for some FFN $\mathcal{K} = \langle \mu, \nu \rangle$ in the UOD \mathcal{U} .

Authors	Score function
Senapati and Yager Senapati and Yager (2020)	$\mathcal{S}_{SY}(\mathcal{K}) = \mu^3 - \nu^3$
Mishra et al. Mishra and Rani (2021)	$\mathcal{S}_{M_1}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}[\mu^3 - \nu^3 - \ln(1 + \pi^3) + 1]$
Sahoo Sahoo (2021)	$\mathcal{S}_{S_1}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mu^3 - \nu^3)$, $\mathcal{S}_{S_2}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{3}(1 + 2\mu^3 - \nu^3)$, $\mathcal{S}_{S_3}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mu^2 - \nu^2) \mu - \nu $
Mishra et al. Mishra et al. (2021)	$\mathcal{S}_{M_2}(\mathcal{K}) = \mu^3 [1 + (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)(1 - \mu^3 - \nu^3)]$
Baranidharan et al. Baranidharan et al. (2022)	$\mathcal{S}_B(\mathcal{K}) = \mu^3 - \nu^3 + \left(\frac{e^{\mu^3 - \nu^3}}{e^{\mu^3 - \nu^3} + 1} - \frac{1}{2}\right)\pi^3$
Sharma et al. Sharma et al. (2023)	$\mathcal{S}_S(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mu - \nu)(\min(\mu, \nu))^2$
Mishra et al. Mishra et al. (2023)	$\mathcal{S}_{M_3}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}[\mu^3 - \nu^3(1 + \pi^3) + 1]$
Mishra et al. Mishra et al. (2024)	$\mathcal{S}_{M_4}(\mathcal{K}) = \left[\frac{\mu^{3q} + (1 - \nu^3)^q}{2}\right]^{1/q}$, $q > 1$
Pathak et al. Pathak et al. (2025)	$\mathcal{S}_{MM}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{4}\left[2\mu^3 - \nu^3 + \frac{\ln(\pi^3 + 1)}{\ln(\pi^3 + 1) + 1} + \mu^9 + 1\right]$
Dutta et al. Dutta et al. (2025)	$\mathcal{S}_P(\mathcal{K}) = 1 + \mu^3 - \nu^3 - \ln(2 - (\mu^3 + \nu^3 - \mu^3\nu^3))$
Ali et al. Ali and Javaid (2025)	$\mathcal{S}_{A_1}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mu^3 - \nu^3)(\min(\mu + \nu, 1))$
Behera and Panda Behera and Panda (2025)	$\mathcal{S}_{BP}(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{2}[1 + \mu^3 - \nu^3 + \tanh(\mu^3 - \nu^3)\pi^3]$
Debbarma et al. Debbarma et al. (2025)	$\mathcal{S}_D(\mathcal{K}) = \frac{1}{3}[1 + \mu^3 - \nu^3 + \log(6 + 4\mu^3 - 5\nu^3)]$

Table 3: Initial decision matrix given by Expert 1 (Linguistic variables)

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
A1	AH	AH	VH	VH	AH	AH	VH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	VH
A2	HG	VH	VH	VH	AH	AH	MH	VH	AH	VH	VH	HG	VH	MH	HG	VH
A3	AH	AH	AH	HG	VH	AH	VH	AH	VH	VH	AH	AH	AH	AH	VH	HG
A4	AH	AH	HG	AH	AH	AH	AH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	AH	HG	VH	VH
A5	LW	ML	ML	LW	ML	ML	VL	LW	MD	LW	ML	LW	ML	VL	MD	VL
A6	EL	VL	EL	EL	LW	LW	EL	EL	LW	LW	VL	VL	EL	VL	EL	EL
A7	MH	MH	MD	MD	HG	HG	MH	MD	MH	MD	MH	HG	MH	MH	HG	MD

Table 4: Initial decision matrix given by Expert 2 (Linguistic variables)

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
A1	VH	AH	AH	AH	VH	VH	AH	AH	AH	HG	HG	VH	VH	AH	HG	VH
A2	HG	VH	HG	AH	MH	MH	VH	VH	HG	HG	MD	HG	HG	AH	MH	VH
A3	HG	VH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	AH	AH	HG	HG	VH	AH	AH	VH	HG
A4	HG	AH	AH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	MH	AH
A5	VL	ML	LW	MD	LW	LW	MD	MD	ML	VL	LW	ML	VL	ML	EL	VL
A6	EL	EL	LW	LW	VL	EL	VL	LW	EL	EL	EL	VL	EL	VL	EL	EL
A7	MD	HG	HG	HG	MD	MD	MD	HG	MD	LW	ML	ML	MD	MH	LW	MD

Table 5: Initial decision matrix given by Expert 3 (Linguistic variables)

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
A1	AH	VH	AH	AH	AH	VH	HG	HG	VH	HG	AH	AH	VH	VH	VH	VH
A2	VH	HG	AH	VH	AH	HG	MH	MH	MH	MH	VH	VH	MH	VH	VH	MH
A3	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	VH	MH	HG	VH	VH	AH	VH	VH	HG	AH	HG
A4	VH	VH	VH	VH	AH	VH	VH	HG	AH	HG	AH	AH	VH	AH	VH	HG
A5	LW	ML	LW	ML	LW	LW	EL	VL	VL	VL	LW	ML	VL	LW	VL	LW
A6	LW	EL	LW	LW	EL	EL	EL	EL	EL	EL	LW	EL	VL	EL	VL	EL
A7	MH	MH	MH	HG	MH	MH	LW	LW	ML	ML	HG	HG	ML	ML	MH	MD

Table 6: Initial decision matrix given by Expert 4 (Linguistic variables)

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
A1	AH	AH	HG	HG	HG	VH	HG	HG	VH	VH	AH	AH	VH	AH	VH	AH
A2	HG	VH	MD	MD	MH	VH	MD	HG	MH	HG	AH	VH	HG	VH	VH	VH
A3	AH	AH	MH	MH	MH	VH	HG	VH	HG	AH	VH	AH	HG	AH	AH	AH
A4	AH	AH	MH	HG	VH	VH	VH	HG	HG	HG	AH	AH	HG	AH	AH	VH
A5	ML	ML	EL	EL	LW	LW	LW	EL	VL	LW	LW	ML	VL	LW	ML	ML
A6	EL	EL	EL	EL	EL	VL	EL	EL	EL	EL	VL	LW	EL	VL	EL	LW
A7	HG	MD	LW	MD	ML	MD	LW	LW	MD	MD	MH	MH	MD	HG	ML	MD

Table 7: Direct-influence matrix rated by Expert 1

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
C1.1	EL	MH	MH	MH	HG	HG	ML	ML	MH	HG	MH	MD	HG	HG	MH	MD
C1.2	ML	EL	MD	ML	MH	ML	ML	MD	MH	MD	MH	MH	HG	ML	ML	HG
C1.3	HG	VH	EL	HG	AH	VH	AH	VH	VH	AH	HG	AH	HG	HG	AH	VH
C1.4	VH	HG	AH	EL	HG	VH	HG	VH	HG	HG	HG	HG	VH	VH	AH	VH
C1.5	ML	VL	VL	VL	EL	MD	MD	ML	EL	MD	VL	MD	MD	MD	MD	EL
C1.6	HG	VH	VH	AH	VH	EL	HG	AH	AH	HG	HG	HG	AH	VH	HG	AH
C1.7	HG	HG	HG	HG	AH	HG	EL	AH	VH	HG	AH	AH	HG	AH	HG	AH
C1.8	MH	ML	MH	ML	HG	ML	HG	EL	HG	ML	HG	MD	ML	HG	ML	MH
C2.1	MH	MH	ML	ML	MH	MH	ML	ML	EL	ML	HG	ML	HG	HG	HG	MH
C2.2	HG	ML	MH	HG	ML	ML	HG	ML	MH	EL	MH	ML	MH	ML	ML	HG
C2.3	MH	ML	MH	MH	ML	ML	MH	MH	HG	ML	EL	ML	MH	ML	ML	MH
C2.4	MH	HG	ML	MD	ML	ML	MH	ML	ML	ML	ML	EL	HG	ML	HG	HG
C2.5	LW	VL	EL	MD	MD	VL	EL	ML	ML	ML	LW	EL	EL	EL	ML	ML
C3.1	EL	MH	VL	ML	EL	EL	ML	EL	MH	MH	VL	VL	MH	EL	VL	VL
C3.2	ML	MH	MH	EL	MH	ML	EL	MH	ML	VL	ML	ML	EL	EL	EL	HG
C3.3	EL	MH	EL	VL	MH	EL	MH	MH	MH	HG	VL	MH	EL	HG	HG	EL

Table 8: Direct-influence matrix rated by Expert 2

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
C1.1	EL	AH	AH	AH	HG	AH	HG	HG	AH	AH	HG	VH	AH	HG	HG	HG
C1.2	VH	EL	HG	VH	VH	VH	AH	VH	MH	MH	HG	HG	VH	MH	HG	HG
C1.3	MD	ML	EL	MD	ML	MD	MH	MD	ML	VL	HG	VL	MD	VL	MD	VL
C1.4	MD	ML	ML	EL	ML	VH	VH	MD	MD	HG	VH	ML	MD	ML	MD	VH
C1.5	HG	ML	ML	VH	EL	MD	MD	VH	MD	MD	VH	VH	MD	VH	HG	HG
C1.6	ML	VH	VH	VH	VH	EL	MD	VH	ML	MH	MD	VH	VH	VH	MD	ML
C1.7	MH	ML	MD	ML	MD	ML	EL	MH	VH	VH	MH	MD	MH	MH	MH	MD
C1.8	AH	HG	AH	AH	AH	VH	AH	EL	HG	AH	AH	AH	HG	AH	VH	AH
C2.1	ML	MD	ML	HG	MD	ML	MD	HG	EL	MH	ML	MH	MH	ML	MD	ML
C2.2	VL	VL	EL	MD	LW	LW	VL	EL	LW	EL	EL	ML	EL	MD	ML	ML
C2.3	MD	HG	MH	ML	MH	MD	HG	HG	HG	ML	EL	MD	ML	MH	MD	MD
C2.4	ML	MH	MD	MH	ML	ML	MH	MD	HG	HG	MD	EL	MD	ML	MD	ML
C2.5	HG	VH	HG	AH	AH	VH	AH	HG	AH	HG	VH	VH	EL	HG	HG	VH
C3.1	EL	MH	VL	ML	EL	EL	ML	EL	MH	MH	VL	VL	MH	EL	VL	VL
C3.2	ML	MH	MH	EL	MH	ML	EL	MH	ML	VL	ML	ML	EL	EL	EL	HG
C3.3	ML	MH	ML	HG	ML	ML	HG	HG	MH	HG	ML	MD	MD	MD	MD	EL

Table 9: Direct-influence matrix rated by Expert 3

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
C1.1	EL	MH	LW	MD	MD	HG	MH	MD	LW	MH	LW	MD	MH	HG	MH	HG
C1.2	ML	EL	MD	MD	MD	MD	ML	EL	HG	ML	HG	HG	MD	MH	MH	ML
C1.3	VL	ML	EL	VL	EL	LW	MH	VL	VL	MH	VL	EL	EL	EL	ML	ML
C1.4	MH	ML	ML	EL	ML	AH	AH	HG	AH	MH	AH	AH	MD	MD	MH	VH
C1.5	HG	ML	ML	VH	EL	MD	MD	VH	MD	MD	VH	VH	MD	VH	HG	HG
C1.6	ML	VH	VH	VH	VH	EL	MD	VH	ML	MH	MD	VH	VH	VH	MD	ML
C1.7	MH	ML	MD	ML	MD	ML	EL	MH	VH	VH	MH	MD	MH	MH	MH	MD
C1.8	AH	HG	AH	AH	AH	VH	AH	EL	HG	AH	AH	AH	HG	AH	VH	AH
C2.1	MD	HG	MH	ML	MH	MD	HG	HG	EL	ML	EL	MH	ML	MH	MH	MH
C2.2	ML	MH	MD	MH	ML	ML	MH	ML	HG	EL	MH	EL	MH	ML	MH	ML
C2.3	HG	VH	HG	AH	AH	VH	AH	HG	AH	HG	EL	VH	EL	HG	HG	VH
C2.4	EL	MH	VL	VL	VL	EL	ML	ML	VL	ML	VL	EL	VL	EL	VL	EL
C2.5	MD	MD	MH	MD	MD	VH	MD	ML	ML	ML	MD	VH	EL	ML	EL	MD
C3.1	ML	MD	ML	VH	ML	ML	VH	VH	MH	VH	ML	MD	MD	EL	MD	EL
C3.2	ML	ML	ML	VH	ML	ML	VH	VH	MH	VH	ML	MD	MD	MD	EL	EL
c3.3	ML	VH	ML	VH	MD	VL	MD	ML	VH	ML	MD	VH	MD	VL	HG	EL

Table 10: Direct-influence matrix rated by Expert 4

Code	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4	C1.5	C1.6	C1.7	C1.8	C2.1	C2.2	C2.3	C2.4	C2.5	C3.1	C3.2	C3.3
C1.1	EL	EL	EL	MD	ML	MD	MD	ML	MD	VL	MD	MD	VL	MD	MD	EL
C1.2	MH	EL	MH	HG	HG	MH	MH	ML	MH	MH	HG	HG	ML	ML	MH	MH
C1.3	MD	ML	EL	VL	EL	VL	MH	VL	VL	MH	VL	EL	EL	EL	ML	ML
C1.4	MD	ML	ML	EL	ML	AH	AH	HG	AH	MH	AH	AH	MD	MD	MH	VH
C1.5	HG	ML	ML	VH	EL	MD	MD	VH	MD	MD	VH	VH	MD	VH	HG	HG
C1.6	ML	VH	VH	VH	VH	EL	MD	VH	ML	MH	MD	VH	VH	VH	MD	ML
C1.7	MH	ML	MD	ML	MD	ML	EL	MH	VH	VH	MH	MD	MH	MH	MH	MD
C1.8	AH	HG	AH	AH	AH	VH	AH	EL	HG	AH	AH	AH	HG	AH	VH	AH
C2.1	ML	MD	ML	HG	MD	ML	MD	HG	EL	MH	ML	MH	MH	ML	MD	ML
C2.2	VL	VL	EL	MD	LW	LW	VL	EL	LW	EL	EL	ML	EL	MD	ML	ML
C2.3	MD	HG	MH	ML	MH	MD	HG	HG	HG	ML	EL	MD	ML	MH	MD	MD
C2.4	ML	MH	MD	MH	ML	ML	MH	MD	HG	HG	MD	EL	MD	ML	MD	ML
C2.5	HG	VH	HG	AH	AH	VH	AH	HG	AH	HG	VH	VH	EL	HG	HG	VH
C3.1	EL	MH	VL	ML	EL	EL	ML	EL	MH	MH	VL	VL	MH	EL	VL	VL
C3.2	ML	MH	MH	EL	MH	ML	EL	MH	ML	VL	ML	ML	EL	EL	EL	HG
C3.3	ML	MH	ML	HG	ML	ML	HG	HG	MH	HG	ML	MD	MD	MD	MD	EL

The resulting Fermatean fuzzy score transformation is used in the implementation, and the *score matrix* S (rows: alternatives; columns: criteria) is normalized into $[0, 1]$ by linear rescaling (row-wise global min/max across the entire matrix). The normalized score matrix \bar{S} is given in Table 12.

References

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Table 11: Aggregated Fermatean fuzzy decision matrix (μ, ν) with alternatives in columns.

Criterion	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7
C_1	(0.979,0.126)	(0.833,0.272)	(0.955,0.170)	(0.955,0.170)	(0.217,0.818)	(0.125,0.940)	(0.644,0.415)
C_2	(0.983,0.118)	(0.882,0.221)	(0.979,0.126)	(0.983,0.118)	(0.350,0.700)	(0.067,0.962)	(0.703,0.374)
C_3	(0.972,0.142)	(0.919,0.217)	(0.968,0.150)	(0.937,0.196)	(0.259,0.790)	(0.166,0.876)	(0.669,0.425)
C_4	(0.972,0.142)	(0.947,0.179)	(0.937,0.196)	(0.947,0.172)	(0.382,0.682)	(0.166,0.876)	(0.721,0.373)
C_5	(0.970,0.145)	(0.955,0.189)	(0.970,0.147)	(0.987,0.109)	(0.264,0.769)	(0.139,0.901)	(0.661,0.425)
C_6	(0.951,0.163)	(0.919,0.226)	(0.951,0.163)	(0.977,0.130)	(0.264,0.769)	(0.136,0.918)	(0.667,0.407)
C_7	(0.943,0.185)	(0.774,0.327)	(0.936,0.199)	(0.951,0.163)	(0.354,0.747)	(0.069,0.959)	(0.510,0.558)
C_8	(0.943,0.185)	(0.856,0.250)	(0.973,0.143)	(0.943,0.185)	(0.357,0.725)	(0.138,0.923)	(0.625,0.503)
C_9	(0.977,0.130)	(0.910,0.241)	(0.951,0.168)	(0.970,0.145)	(0.376,0.696)	(0.134,0.929)	(0.536,0.508)
C_{10}	(0.929,0.206)	(0.819,0.285)	(0.910,0.209)	(0.938,0.189)	(0.159,0.856)	(0.134,0.929)	(0.408,0.634)
C_{11}	(0.949,0.176)	(0.888,0.247)	(0.966,0.157)	(0.959,0.154)	(0.264,0.769)	(0.134,0.902)	(0.653,0.448)
C_{12}	(0.979,0.126)	(0.847,0.258)	(0.963,0.149)	(0.979,0.126)	(0.320,0.728)	(0.118,0.907)	(0.710,0.412)
C_{13}	(0.951,0.163)	(0.819,0.285)	(0.975,0.136)	(0.947,0.172)	(0.239,0.835)	(0.063,0.967)	(0.536,0.508)
C_{14}	(0.966,0.146)	(0.938,0.195)	(0.980,0.131)	(0.950,0.174)	(0.260,0.793)	(0.091,0.921)	(0.640,0.442)
C_{15}	(0.939,0.186)	(0.821,0.284)	(0.959,0.154)	(0.895,0.230)	(0.354,0.755)	(0.063,0.967)	(0.637,0.496)
C_{16}	(0.927,0.183)	(0.869,0.237)	(0.871,0.260)	(0.947,0.176)	(0.202,0.847)	(0.101,0.963)	(0.500,0.500)

Table 12: Normalized score matrix \bar{S} (all values in $[0, 1]$).

Alt.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	C_7	C_8	C_9	C_{10}	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{13}	C_{14}	C_{15}	C_{16}
A_1	0.9682	0.9737	0.9575	0.9575	0.9543	0.9275	0.9155	0.9155	0.9650	0.8970	0.9252	0.9682	0.9275	0.9493	0.9114	0.8950
A_2	0.7787	0.8382	0.8834	0.9212	0.9323	0.8818	0.7139	0.8063	0.8696	0.7626	0.8424	0.7955	0.7626	0.9088	0.7653	0.8210
A_3	0.9333	0.9682	0.9518	0.9079	0.9552	0.9275	0.9064	0.9594	0.9272	0.8717	0.9483	0.9455	0.9621	0.9694	0.9388	0.8211
A_4	0.9333	0.9737	0.9079	0.9216	0.9796	0.9650	0.9275	0.9155	0.9543	0.9090	0.9388	0.9682	0.9216	0.9267	0.8529	0.9219
A_5	0.2320	0.3499	0.2619	0.3695	0.2819	0.2819	0.3135	0.3325	0.3580	0.1884	0.2819	0.3232	0.2153	0.2597	0.3068	0.2007
A_6	0.0860	0.0544	0.1663	0.1663	0.1361	0.1144	0.0587	0.1084	0.0998	0.0998	0.1338	0.1273	0.0477	0.1095	0.0477	0.0537
A_7	0.5977	0.6478	0.6114	0.6613	0.6061	0.6149	0.4795	0.5581	0.5114	0.4065	0.5942	0.6444	0.5114	0.5880	0.5683	0.5000

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